

Learned Edge-Guided Multiple Attention-based Generative Adversarial Network for Single Image Super-Resolution

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Abstract- It is well-known that recovering high-frequency details from low-resolution images remains a major challenge in single image super-resolution. This work presents a multiple attention-based generative adversarial network that leverages a learned edge detector to enhance structural details in the reconstructed images. A multiple attention-based block is designed to capture multi-level contextual information and different attention-based features. In addition, a Scale-Invariant Feature Transform-based loss function is employed to ensure the preservation of scale-invariant features and reducing discrepancies between the generated and ground-truth images. Comprehensive experiments on standard datasets demonstrate that the proposed approach consistently outperforms existing state-of-the-art models and achieves higher PSNR and SSIM values while delivering perceptually superior results with lower LPIPS scores.

Keywords - Single Image Super Resolution, Generative Adversarial Network, Hybrid Attention, Scale-Invariant Feature Transform, Learned Edge Detector

I. INTRODUCTION

Single Image Super-Resolution (SISR) aims to reconstruct a high-resolution (HR) image from a single low-resolution (LR) input [1]. The problem is inherently ill-posed because multiple HR images may correspond to the same LR input, making the recovery of fine image details highly challenging. In particular, SISR models often struggle with restoring high-frequency information, avoiding visual artifacts, and faithfully representing complex structures [2].

Traditional interpolation [3,4] and optimization-based approaches [5,6] provide limited improvements, as they cannot adequately model the intricate details and non-linear mapping between LR and HR domains. With the advent of deep learning, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [7,8] have demonstrated remarkable progress by learning hierarchical feature representations that improve reconstruction quality. However, CNN-based models frequently produce over-smoothed outputs and fail to recover sharp and visually appealing details. Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [9] have further advanced SISR by improving perceptual realism, yet many GAN-based frameworks struggle to preserve fine textures and high-frequency content [10].

One key limitation arises from the reliance on Residual-in-Residual Dense Blocks (RRDB) [11,26] and uniform convolutional filters, which are inadequate for modeling long-range dependencies and complex geometries. Moreover, the absence of adaptive mechanisms, such as attention and multi-scale feature extraction, restricts the ability to focus on informative regions. These drawbacks not only compromise visual quality but also increase computational cost due to the heavy use of filters. Another critical gap in existing methods is the lack of high-level feature preservation, mainly edges, which is essential for generating sharper reconstructions.

To address these challenges, this paper proposes a Learned Edge-guided Multiple Attention-based Generative Adversarial Network (LEMA-GAN) for SISR. The main contributions of this work are:

- Multiple attention-based mechanism: A block combining variable-size filters and multiple attention strategies i.e channel attention and multi-head attention to extract diverse features and strengthen contextual representation.
- Edge-guided learning: A learned edge detector is integrated into the network to enhance structural fidelity and preserve fine details in the super-resolved images.
- Scale-invariant supervision: A SIFT-based loss function is employed to maintain scale-invariant features, reducing structural inconsistencies between reconstructed and reference images.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II details the proposed method. Section III reports the experimental details and results. Finally, Section IV concludes the paper.

II. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

2.1 Network Overview:

The overall architecture of the proposed LEMA-GAN model is depicted in Figure1, comprising a Main Branch (MB), an Edge Branch (EB), and a Reconstruction Block (RB).

Figure 1. Framework of Learned Edge-guided Multiple Attention-based Generative Adversarial Network (LEMA-GAN)

The MB extracts structural features from LR input, while the EB processes learned edge maps. Their outputs are fused and passed through RB to produce the final HR image. The Reconstruction Block receives two types of feature maps as input: the upsampled structure maps from the Main Branch (M_m) and the upsampled edge maps from the Edge Branch (E_m). These maps are concatenated at the Fusion node to form enriched structural representations, which are subsequently processed by the reconstruction block (RB) to generate the final super-resolved image (HR):

$$HR = RB(\text{Concatenate}(M_m, E_m)) \quad (1)$$

Upscaled Structure Maps: The structure maps (M_m) are generated from the Main Branch. Starting with the LR image, an initial convolution layer extracts shallow feature maps (F_{ms}). These shallow features are then passed through a sequence of 16 Multiple Attention Blocks (MABs), producing deep feature maps (F_{md}). Each MAB block consists of four steps to extract different types of features using four different approaches i.e multi-scale convolution with varying kernels, dilated convolutions for enlarged receptive fields, channel attention to prioritize informative channels, and spatial/global attention to capture long-range dependencies, respectively. This structure enables rich multi-feature extraction and representation. The obtained shallow and deep features are combined at the Plus node to enhance representation and then upsampled using a series of ‘UPCONV’ layers, yielding the final upscaled structure maps.

Upscaled Edge Maps: The edge maps (E_m) are produced from the Edge Branch. First, the LR image is processed by a learned edge detector ($L(\bullet)$) to extract a low-resolution edge map. An initial convolution operation then generates shallow edge features (F_{es}), which are refined by four stacked MAB layers to produce deep edge features (F_{ed}). To enrich these features, low-level information from the Main Branch is incorporated via skip connections. The shallow and deep edge features are fused at the Plus node and then upsampled using ‘UPCONV’ layers to form the enhanced edge maps. Moreover, the Edge Branch outputs a super-resolved edge map, which is directly included in the objective function of the model to further guide structural consistency in the reconstructed image.

2.2 Objective Function:

The objective function combines pixel loss function (L_p), feature loss function (L_f), adversarial loss function for generator (L_a^G) and discriminator network (L_a^D), and SIFT-based loss function (L_s). Pixel and feature losses ensure content fidelity, adversarial loss improves realism, and SIFT-based loss enforces scale-invariant reconstruction. The weighted sum of these terms balances accuracy and perceptual quality. The formulations of the four loss functions are represented as:

$$L_p = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{k=1}^B |I_{HR} - I_{GT}|_1 \quad (2)$$

$$L_f = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{k=1}^B |\phi(I_{HR}) - \phi(I_{GT})|_1 \quad (3)$$

$$L_a^G = -\log(D(I_{HR})), \quad L_a^D = -\log(1 - D(I_{HR})) - \log(D(I_{GT})) \quad (4)$$

$$L_s = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{k=1}^B |v(I_{HR}) - v(I_{LR})|_2 \quad (5)$$

Where, I_{LR} , I_{HR} , I_{GT} , B denote input LR image, generated HR image, target ground truth (GT) image, and batch size, respectively. ϕ is the features of the images extracted from a trained VGG model[12], $D()$ denotes the probability assigned by the discriminator, reflecting the likelihood of the input being real or synthesized, and $v()$ is the 128-dimensional descriptor vector corresponding to the i^{th} keypoint of the image.

These four loss functions are applied between the reconstructed high-resolution (HR) images and their ground-truth (GT) counterparts ($L_p^i, L_f^i, L_a^i, L_{s-hr}^i$). Additionally, pixel loss function, adversarial loss function, and the SIFT loss function [25] are also applied on the edge (L_p^e, L_a^e, L_{s-hr}^e), tensor (L_p^t, L_a^t, L_{s-hr}^t), and gradient (L_p^g, L_a^g, L_{s-hr}^g) maps derived from both HR and GT images. To further enhance structural consistency, the SIFT loss function is also applied between HR and LR images (L_{s-lr}^i) along with their corresponding feature maps, namely edge maps (L_{s-lr}^e), tensor maps (L_{s-lr}^t), and gradient maps (L_{s-lr}^g).

The gradient map of images is obtained by computing the gradient magnitude at each pixel location. On the other hand, the tensor map enhances structural representation and is defined for each image channel T_c as:

$$T_c = \sqrt{(I_x)^2 + (I_{xy})^2 + (I_y)^2} \quad (6)$$

Here, $I_{xy} = I_x \times I_y$, with I_x and I_y denote the Gaussian-smoothed Sobel gradient maps of the image in the horizontal and vertical directions, respectively. The edge map is generated by applying a learned edge detector,

which captures distinct and accurate structural boundaries. The SIFT operator is employed to extract scale-invariant descriptors, guiding the reconstruction of fine spectral details such as textures and edges. These different maps emphasize complementary aspects of the image, including local intensity transitions, coarse structural layouts, and delicate edge details. By combining pixel, feature, adversarial, and scale-invariant loss functions, the framework enforces both accurate content restoration and perceptual realism.

The complete objective function is defined as:

$$L_{total} = a_1 L_p^i + a_2 L_p^e + a_3 L_p^t + a_4 L_p^g + b_1 L_f^i + c_1 L_a^i + c_2 L_a^e + c_3 L_a^t + c_4 L_a^g + d_1 (L_{s-lr}^i + L_{s-lr}^e + L_{s-lr}^t + L_{s-lr}^g) + d_2 (L_{s-hr}^i + L_{s-hr}^e + L_{s-hr}^t + L_{s-hr}^g) \quad (7)$$

This objective function ensures that the generated super-resolved image maintain high content fidelity while also providing superior perceptual quality.

III. EXPERIMENT AND RESULT

3.1 Training Details-

The 'DIV2K' dataset is adopted for model training and validation, which includes 800 images for training, 100 for validation, and 100 for testing. The proposed LEMA-GAN network is implemented using the 'PyTorch' framework in Python and trained on an 'NVIDIA GTX 3070Ti GPU'. To accelerate convergence, the model is initialized with parameters from a previously trained network [11]. In the training phase, both ground-truth (GT) and low-resolution (LR) samples are divided into patches of size 128×128 (HR) and 32×32 (LR). A mini-batch of 4 is used, and data augmentation techniques such as random flipping and rotation are applied to increase diversity. The weights associated with the loss function (Equation 7) are determined via grid search, leading to the following settings: (0.001, 0.001, 0.5, 0.01, 1, 0.001, 0.001, 0.001, 0.001, 0.001, 0.001) for $(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, b_1, c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, d_1, d_2)$. The optimization process employs the ADAM optimizer [13], with hyperparameters set to $\beta_1 = 0.9$ and $\beta_2 = 0.999$. Training begins with a learning rate of 1×10^{-4} , which is progressively reduced by a factor of 0.5 at 15 scheduled intervals. The network is trained for 50,000 iterations, which takes nearly 14 hours to complete. Stable convergence is achieved through careful adjustment of the learning rate schedule and the weighting of loss components.

3.2 Results and Discussions-

For quantitative evaluation, the proposed LEMA-GAN model is tested on widely used benchmark datasets, including Set14 [14], BSD100 [15], Urban100 [16], PIRM_val [17], and DIV2K_val [18]. The performance of our method is compared against several state-of-the-art approaches such as SRGAN [19], ESRGAN [11], SPSR [20], LDL [21], and InvSR [22]. Evaluation is carried out using standard metrics—PSNR, SSIM [23], and LPIPS [24]. The comparative results are summarized in Table 1. From the results, it can be observed that the LEMA-GAN model provides higher PSNR values on all datasets compared to competing methods. In addition, it consistently achieves the lowest LPIPS scores across all test datasets, highlighting its ability to recover fine structural information and generate perceptually convincing high-resolution images.

Table 1. Metric results of the proposed network (LEMA-GAN) and various other models used in the study.

Method	Metric	Set14	BSD100	Urban100	PIRM_val	DIV2K_val
Bicubic	PSNR	24.410	23.920	22.646	25.508	27.040
	SSIM	0.662	0.635	0.640	0.698	0.765
	LPIPS	0.410	0.603	0.473	0.214	0.392
SRGAN [19]	PSNR	25.950	25.080	23.400	25.457	27.030
	SSIM	0.692	0.684	0.687	0.664	0.768
	LPIPS	0.244	0.331	0.155	0.160	0.223
ESRGAN [11]	PSNR	26.260	25.380	23.269	25.182	27.460
	SSIM	0.721	0.688	0.691	0.660	0.781
	LPIPS	0.241	0.328	0.122	0.149	0.213

SPSR [20]	PSNR	26.640	25.505	24.799	25.702	28.832
	SSIM	0.793	0.658	0.948	0.681	0.782
	LPIPS	0.132	0.161	0.118	0.147	0.151
LDL [21]	PSNR	25.836	26.111	24.235	26.334	28.951
	SSIM	0.688	0.682	0.721	0.704	0.795
	LPIPS	0.114	0.118	0.116	0.109	0.112
InvSR [22]	PSNR	21.720	22.607	20.826	22.573	23.969
	SSIM	0.586	0.576	0.583	0.585	0.583
	LPIPS	0.129	0.160	0.118	0.126	0.114
LEMA-GAN (proposed)	PSNR	26.824	26.735	25.208	27.511	31.732
	SSIM	0.796	0.714	0.792	0.755	0.814
	LPIPS	0.103	0.101	0.103	0.105	0.101

For qualitative assessment, visual comparisons are carried out on selected samples, including ‘13’ and ‘15’ from PIRM_val and ‘img_030’ from Urban100. The corresponding results are shown in Figure 2. As seen in the enlarged regions, the proposed LEMA-GAN model produces sharper high-frequency details, effectively reduces unwanted artifacts, and maintains better structural consistency in challenging image regions when compared with existing methods.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced a Learned Edge-Guided Multiple Attention-based GAN (LEGMA-GAN) for single image super-resolution. Unlike earlier frameworks that rely on handcrafted edge detectors such as Sobel, Canny, the proposed model integrates a learned edge detector that adaptively extracts more accurate and informative edge features to guide the reconstruction process. In combination with the proposed multi-attention block which is capable of capturing local, global, spatial, and channel-specific dependencies, the network effectively preserves fine structures and restores high-frequency details. Furthermore, a SIFT-based loss function was incorporated to enforce scale-invariant supervision, ensuring that both structural consistency and perceptual fidelity are maintained in the generated images. Experimental evaluations demonstrated that the model delivers sharper and more visually appealing results. Although the current design balances quality and efficiency, future work will focus on developing lightweight extensions of the proposed framework to enable real-time deployment in resource-constrained environments. Overall, this study highlights the importance of combining edge-aware learning, multi-attention mechanisms, and scale-invariant constraints to push the boundaries of high-quality single image super-resolution.

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